

CONTENT AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CONCEPT OF TOLERANCE

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Annotation. This article theoretically analyzes the philosophical, pedagogical and legal foundations of the concept of tolerance and reveals the content.

Key words: Tolerance, enlightenment, reconciliation, upbringing, culture of tolerance, historical, national identity.

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ И ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ПОНЯТИЯ ТОЛЕРАНТНОСТИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье теоретически анализируются философско-педагогические и правовые основания понятия толерантности и раскрывается содержание.

Ключевые слова: Толерантность, просвещение, примирение, воспитание, культура толерантности, исторический, национальное самосознание.

ТОЛЕРАНТЛИК ТУШУНЧАСИНИНГ МАЗМУН-МОҲИЯТИ ВА НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛИ

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Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада толерантликни тушунчасининг фалсафий, педагогик ва ҳуқуқий асослари жиҳатдан назарий таҳлил қилинган ва мазмун-моҳияти очиқ берилган.

Таянч сўзлар: Толерантлик, маърифатпарварлик, мураса, таълим-тарбия, толерантлик маданияти, тарихий, миллий ўзликни англаш тарихий, миллий ўзликни англаш.

The religious and worldly tolerance, generosity, hospitality and kindness of the Uzbek people are considered to be its ancient virtues and have been formed, developed and improved over the centuries. Such qualities were important for our nation to persevere through the most difficult tests of history.

That is why it is necessary to constantly strengthen the moral basis of education and enrich it with the heritage of ancestors. If we need happiness, honor, peace, stability, pleasure, honor, honor and attention, we should learn the methods of raising the next generation as soon as possible and educate our children based on these methods and rules.

In the address of the leader of our country to the Oliy Majlis, the following points are mentioned: "In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only the youth, but also the members of our society as a whole, first of all, knowledge and high spirituality are needed. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, error. As the sages of the East said, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance!"

Based on the main criteria of the national-spiritual education of our well-thought-out citizens, the opinion of the President indicated a number of tasks that are important in the formation of tolerance in the maturation of the young generation and based on their philosophical and moral characteristics. Increasing the effectiveness of reforms in the social and spiritual spheres is an important task for the representatives of each sphere.

The Jadidism movement, which emerged in a number of eastern and Muslim countries at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, has deep historical roots in Turkestan. It should be noted that our country was not left out of these processes of great socio-political and educational importance, on the contrary, it became one of the centers of this movement. "Jadids, who were the leading representatives of their time, came out with the idea of spreading knowledge

and enlightenment, and achieving national development by fundamentally reforming the field of education in extremely complicated and difficult conditions".

Pedagogically scientific-theoretical study of tolerance thinking and culture, introducing it to all stages of the educational system, understanding its pedagogic foundations have begun. Pedagogically scientific-theoretical study of tolerance thinking shows that it has developed in the following directions during the years of independence:

1. Scientific-theoretical understanding of the principle of religious tolerance within the concept of tolerance from the perspective of philosophical, political, social, sociological, historical, understanding of national identity and national ideology, democratic and secular society, study of its general theoretical aspects (Z. Kadirova, D.A. Alimova, G.N. Navro'zova, M. Vohidova, A. Azizkho'jaev).

In general, the dictionary meaning of the word "tolerance" is explained as follows. The term tolerance comes from the Latin word and is used in two different meanings:

- first of all, tolerance towards other people's way of life, behavior, customs, feelings.

- secondly, resistance to adverse emotional factors.

The word "tolerance" was originally used in the fields of biology and medicine, and the term was applied to people who lacked immunity. Tolerance was not understood as a specific concept by different cultures and depended on the historical experience of the communities. Although the concept of tolerance is interpreted differently in the languages of different peoples and nations of the world, it does not change in essence. As a result of our research, it would be appropriate to classify this concept as follows. The dictionary meanings of terms describing tolerance in several languages of the world are as follows:

In English, "tolerance" is the unquestioning acceptance of a person or a reality;

- in French - to be attentive to the political or religious way of thinking and views of others;

- and in Arabic sources - grace is used in the meaning of forgiveness, mercy, patience;

- in Chinese - it means to be kind to the actions of others, to show tolerance towards others;

- In Russian explanatory dictionaries - to tolerate is interpreted in the meaning of endurance. Studying religious and national tolerance and inculcating it in the minds and hearts of people, especially our youth, has always been one of the main tasks facing science.

"Interreligious tolerance means that representatives of different religious denominations live together in harmony for good goals and intentions, and work for the development of human society".

This definition is widely used in textbooks and dictionaries.

According to Professor A. Ochildiev: "religious tolerance, expressed in modern language, has roots in ancient times. Religious tolerance has always served as a kind of shield against religious hostility. He paved the way for the coexistence of different faiths in the same time and space, for the formation of cooperation and solidarity. This, in turn, served the peace and development of the country, the development of universal culture and spirituality".

Based on socio-demographic factors, scientists distinguish the following areas of tolerance:

- gender tolerance - not treating the representatives of the other gender incorrectly, abandoning the ideas that one gender is based on the other gender;

- age tolerance - correct acceptance of age-related characteristics of a person (inability of the elderly to understand the young, insufficient knowledge and experience of the young, etc.);

- tolerance related to the level of education - to be patient with the thoughts and actions of people with a relatively low level of education.

- inter-national tolerance - treating representatives of different nationalities with respect, not assuming that the shortcomings and negative actions of

representatives of one nationality are also present in other people belonging to this nationality.

Building a culture of tolerance is a complex process, and its effectiveness may have different indicators in different regions. However, the general result is that it is necessary to educate young students in the spirit of tolerance and to instill in their minds the sincere application of concepts such as compatriots and compatriots to all nations and peoples who live in the space called Motherland. For this, it is necessary to seriously observe the relations related to tolerance in the daily activities of pedagogues and give them a vital meaning.

In our opinion, in order to educate young people in the spirit of tolerance in the process of education and training, in the system of higher and secondary special education, it is necessary to operate on the basis of an improved complex that includes all the features of the formation of a "perfect person", to adopt the principles of tolerance as one of the main features of teaching young people to live in modern societies, based on the full content of the concept of tolerance, the logical coherence and moral integrity of the principles of tolerance, the ability of a person to enter into interpersonal and inter-community relations, the right way out of various situations based on tolerance and the correct conclusion of problems should be nurtured.

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